

Green Economy Dilemma: An Inquiry in to Potential Trade-offs in Agriculture Sector in Nepal

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Abstract

Government of Nepal is initiating various Green Economy interventions without knowing its probable trade-offs. Among three definitional pillars of the green economy mentioned in the purposed framework prepared by the government, this paper aims at gauging the social pillar focusing only the agriculture sector. The NLSS-III data is used to see whether there is any gender discrimination in terms of wages in agriculture sector. The labor productivity at macro stature is analyzed using annual time series data produced by CBS where usual Solow residual is estimated. It is concluded that the Labor remained pivotal in growth performance during last three decades in Nepal where relative role of capital and total factor productivity remain scanty. It's imperative to know the growth-employment trade-offs in Nepal before full-fledged green intervention. At the same time, the role of proposed green intervention on total factor productivity stipulation is unknown. And, Nepalese agriculture sector is not green.

INTRODUCTION

It has been realized that Earth's resources are limited just. The developed nations have also realized that their present form of economic growth is reaching its limit as stated by BMZ (2011). Global demand for energy and resource is soaring, forests are shrinking, drinking water is becoming scarce and ecosystems are vanishing along with their flora and fauna. It is estimated that unabated climate change could cost as much as 20 per cent of global GDP by 2050 and cause widespread impoverishment (Stem 2006). It is not only flora and fauna which are vanishing along with biodiversity; so are numerous opportunities to pursue a sustainable, pro-poor development pathway. There are over 120,000 protected areas on Earth that provide humankind with ecosystem services valued up to US\$ 5.2 trillion per year, so their destruction or degradation would have massive economic costs. By contrast, the investments necessary to conserve these areas add up around US\$ 45 billion a year (TEEB 2009). It is signaling for the alternative economic growth paradigm. Consequently, the concept of Green Economy is emerging by adhering to new economic growth paradigm; friendly to the ecosystems and contribute to poverty alleviation.

The green growth, which is anonymous to green economy henceforth, was a center of policy discussion during the Rio+20 Conference. The conference provided platform for various stakeholders to show their

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commitments on strong sustainability which is the resultant of keeping resource base less affected while ensuring the thrust of sustainable development. It is alternative debate on how individual economies can pursue more sustainable growth paths. It is anticipated that that the green economy will create more opportunities than risks for the industrialized, emerging and developing countries alike. It would have been offering new horizons for humankind to benefit from nature and environment that can be an effective tool to combat poverty and hunger. In the meantime, governments around the globe are seeking ways to define and shape 'green economy' into meaningful policies that advance inclusive economic growth while enhancing environmental protection and social progress. Some governments like: Guyana, Ireland, Japan, South Africa etc. have already prepared their green economy frameworks of action while some others like: Azerbaijan, Brazil, Peru, South Korea etc. are in the process of designing it. The Government of Nepal is also preparing various environmental friendly development interventions right from climate change related public expenditure tracking to green growth framework for following periodic plan.

Definition and Terminology

The term Green Economy was first coined in a pioneering 1989 report for the Government of the United Kingdom by a group of leading environmental economists, entitled *Blueprint for a Green Economy* (Pearce et al. 1989 cited in UNDESA 2012). Apart from in the title of the report, there is no further reference to green economy and it appears that the term was used as an afterthought by the authors. In 2008, the term was revived in the context of discussions on the policy response to multiple global crises. In the context of the financial crisis and concerns of a global recession, UNEP championed the idea of 'green stimulus package' and identified specific areas where large-scale public investment could kick-start a 'green economy' (AtKisson 2012). The same year later, UNEP launched its Green Economy Initiative (GEI) to provide analysis and policy support for investment in green sectors and for greening resource.

The GEI captures the notion of the vulnerability of human welfare, which can be understood as the consequences of the widespread application of an unsustainable model of economic development. It addresses the concerns raised repeatedly over the course of the past 40 years that were fervently expressed in the world gatherings: UN Conference on the Human Environment 1972 in Stockholm, Earth Summit 1992 in Rio, and World Summit on Sustainable Development 2002 in Johannesburg. These concerns likewise have been raised in publications over the course of that period, such as World Conservation Strategy-Living Resources Conservation for Sustainable Development (1980), Our Common Future (1987), and Caring for the Earth- A Strategy for Sustainable Living (1991).

In the wake of the worst financial and economic crisis in generations, UNEP also called for a Global Green New Deal (GGND) and released a policy brief to G20 heads of state in March 2009. The policy brief presented a strong case for the active 'greening' of fiscal stimulus packages, and urged the heads of state to turn the crisis into an opportunity by enabling a global green economy driven by massive job creation from a more efficient use of resources, energy-efficient building and construction, widespread use of clean and modern public transport, the scaling up of renewable energy, sustainable waste management, and sustainable agriculture that reflects the latest thinking in ecosystem management and biodiversity and water conservation (UNEP 2009).

In 2010, the UN General Assembly agreed that Green Economy in the context of sustainable development and poverty eradication would form one of the two specific themes for Rio+20 (resolution 64/236), which led to a great deal of international attention on it. One of the key reports was the flagship Green Economy Report released by UNEP in 2011 under GEI. This was followed by a series of publications by other agencies

such as UNCTAD, UNDESA and UNCSD Secretariat, which attempted to elaborate on the concept and outline guiding principles, benefits, risks and emerging international experience. In Rio+20 Conference 2012, the concept was thoroughly discussed, and the outcomes document 'The Future We Want' maintained that the 'determination to pursue the green economy in the context of sustainable development and poverty eradication' (UNCSD 2012).

In last several years, major international organizations have launched Green Economy (GE)/Green Growth (GG) initiatives to integrate economic, environmental, and social imperatives. Besides UNEP, the important organizations who have been advocating in international forums to integrate conservation and development themes and establish collaborative platforms where all concerned stakeholders could contribute to the health of the planet. The important players fostering the GE include Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), International Labor Organization (ILO), Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO), World Bank, multilateral and bilateral institutions, member countries, regional forums, business and civil society groups, universities and regional commissions and international and national NGOs among others.

There is as yet no agreed definition or indeed a generally accepted concept of what constitutes a green economy. At least eight separate definitions were identified in recent publications (TABLE: 1). UNEP has defined the green economy as "one that results in improved human well-being and social equity, while significantly reducing environmental risks and ecological scarcities. It is low carbon, resource efficient, and socially inclusive" (UNEP 2011). This definition has been cited in a number of more recent reports including UNEMG and OECD. The UNEP assumes that greening is a new engine for growth, emphasizing sectoral opportunities, addressing hurdles and enabling conditions, demonstrating the value of ecosystem and biodiversity, capturing these values, and reversing the vicious cycle of environmental losses and persistent poverty by reversing the vicious cycle of environmental losses and persistent poverty.

TABLE 1: Definitions of Green Economy

SN	Definition
1	One that results in improved human well-being and social equity, while significantly reducing environmental risks and ecological scarcities. It is low carbon, resource efficient, and socially inclusive. In a green economy, growth in income and employment should be driven by public and private investments that reduce carbon emissions and pollution, enhance energy and resource efficiency, and prevent the loss of biodiversity and ecosystem services (UNEP 2011).
2	A system of economic activities related to the production, distribution and consumption of goods and services that result in improved human well-being over the long term, while not exposing future generations to significant environmental risks or ecological scarcities (UNEP 2009).
3	An economy that results in improved human well-being and reduced inequalities, while not exposing future generations to significant environmental risks and ecological scarcities. It seeks to bring long-term societal benefits to short-term activities aimed at mitigating environmental risk. A green economy is an enabling component of the overarching goal of sustainable development (UNCTAD 2011)
4	Green economy is 'a resilient economy that provides a better quality of life for all within the ecological limits of the planet'(Green Economy Coalition 2010).

5	'Green Economy' is described as an economy in which economic growth and environmental responsibility work together in a mutually reinforcing fashion while supporting progress on social development (International Chamber of Commerce 2011)
6	The Green Economy is not a state but a process of Transformation and a constant dynamic progression. The Green Economy does away with the systemic distortions and dis-functionalities of the current mainstream economy and results in human well-being and equitable access to opportunity for all people, while safeguarding environmental and economic integrity in order to remain within the planet's finite carrying capacity. The Economy cannot be Green without being Equitable. (Danish 92 Group 2012)
7	The green economy involves largely new economic activities and must provide an important entry-point for broad-based black economic empowerment, addressing the needs of women and youth entrepreneurs and offering opportunities for enterprises in the social economy (Government of South Africa 2011)
8	Green economy can be seen as a lens for focusing on and seizing opportunities to advance economic and environmental goals simultaneously (From: <i>Rio+20 Objectives and Themes of the Conference</i> . UNCSO 2011)

Source: UNDESA (2012)

At international level, a very often used terminology is Green Growth (GG). The GG describes an economic growth strategy based on the ecological restructuring of existing economic processes, creating jobs and income generation opportunities in new green sectors of the economy and minimizing environmental impacts. The concept of GG is therefore of particular relevance in the development policy debate.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Some initiatives on green economy have taken place in Nepal, albeit mainly in the forms of dialogues and seminars on the subject. While some of these were national-level programs focusing only on Nepal, others were regional/international-level programs, which too, however, discussed the issues in the Nepalese context, although in varying degrees. A summary of these different initiatives, in chronological order, is presented in the table below (Table 2).

TABLE2: Initiatives on Green Economy taken in Nepal

Date	Initiative undertaken	Initiators	Remarks
National-level			
18 NOV 2010	Workshop on Environments of the Poor in the context of Climate Change and GE	NPC/GoN supported Poverty Environment Initiative (PEI) Program	Major objective was to provide inputs to NPC in adopting poverty and climate responsive programs in the next periodic plan. The green economy aspects were not discussed much.
25 SEPT 2012	GE Development Dialogue	NPC in collaboration with Himalayan Climate Initiative (HCI) and CNI supported by PEI	Focus was on the green aspects of Nepalese agriculture and not much on manufacturing/industry. The discussions also could not enter into depths of the subject.

23 NOV 2012	Consultation Meeting	PEI/SPMC/ National Planning Commission	Interdisciplinary expert interaction on purposed framework to incorporate key ingredients of GE and green development in the periodic development plans.
30 May- 3 June 2011	Regional International level Bio-trade and Green Economy Week	UNEP, UNCTAD and GIZ	Focus was on the contribution of bio-trade to GE (How Nepal having the niche in bio-trade should seize the opportunity?)
5-7 SEP 2011	International Conference on GE and Sustainable Mountain Development	ICIMOD, supported by UNEP and IDRC	A focused program on GE and mountain systems that discussed several specific issues on how mountain countries should go ahead with greening their mountain systems and other countries should support.
3-5 May 2012	Regional Workshop on Environmental Mainstreaming for a Green Economy	Asian Center for Environment Management and Sustainable Development	Discussion and experiences sharing with other South Asian countries on environmental mainstreaming and GE. Existing GE activities were identified and calls were made to strengthen them as well as adopt them.
25-29 September 2012	Asia Pacific Graduates' Youth Forum on Green Economy,	Small Earth Nepal (SEN); University of Colorado; ICIMO; GON; SD; USAID/OFDA; Small Earth Australia (SEA) and University of Saskatchewan	Capacity building of young graduates dedicated to and engaged in sustainability issues, and to facilitate the sharing of their knowledge and information on GE, environmental governance and climate adaptation.

Among the initiatives summarized above, the consultation meeting organized National Planning Commission (NPC) in 23 November, 2012 finalized one GE framework. It was an interdisciplinary expert interaction on purposed framework to incorporate key ingredients of GE and green development in the periodic development plans. It pointed out the need for gradually adoption of green economy policies in key economic sectors. The proposed GE framework recommends that **Agriculture and Forestry, Infrastructure and energy, and Tourism** should be given high and first priority for green intervention in Nepal.

Theoretically accepting the definition of GE given by UNEP (2011), the proposed GE framework evaluated Nepalese Agriculture sector (Table 3). It argues that in terms of carbon emission angle, it is very low and can maintained low as such. Regarding the resource efficiency angle, it is medium and can be maintained medium in post intervention time as well. Similarly, it is argued that Nepalese agriculture sector is socially inclusive currently and can be maintained even if after some green economic policy interventions. Though there are no specific and well accepted tool kits or methodology to assess whether a particular sector is green, the framework used the expert's perception to do so. Among scantily available assessment framework, the Eberts (2011) proposed 'Framework and Tools for Assessing and Understanding the Green Economy at the Local Level' seems relatively convincing and applicable in Nepalese case. It raises some straight forward question like: (i) What does a shift to a green economy mean for jobs and skills?, (ii) In which sectors are jobs likely to be created and/or destroyed?, (iii) Does moving to a low-carbon economy necessarily mean lower productivity, lower wages, and slower economic and job growth?, (iv) is the green economy the next

...wave of growth and innovation that will stimulate growth at the local and national levels, raising overall standard of living?, and (v) What are the skills and technology needed to accommodate growth in the green economy?

TABLE 3. Status GE Pillars in Agriculture & Forestry in Nepal

SN	GE Pillars	Current Status	Post Intervention Status
1	Carbon Emission	Low	Low
2	Resource Efficiency	Medium	Medium
3	Socially Inclusive	High	High

Source: NPC(2012), Draft GE Framework

In this context; there are sufficient rooms to be imperative regarding the degree and distance of agreed greenness of Nepalese agriculture sector. Beside this there might be some trade-offs of green interventions. The trade-offs can be tracked based on the defined GE Pillars like: (i) Is our agriculture sector resource efficient? And (ii) Is our agriculture sector socially inclusive in terms of gender?

METHODOLOGY

To better answer these queries from policy view point, estimation of the size of the Green Economy and Green Jobs is must. The size of the green economy and the greenness of the activities at disagreed firm would be instrumental for better policy formulation. It will also help to build robust monitoring and evaluation of the interventions. Criteria for identifying green activities and methodologies for estimating the size of the green economy vary somewhat, yielding different estimates. But, the analysis at this scale is beyond the scope of this paper.

Before green intervention in selected sectors, it is necessary to know the current Green Economy status of the sectors in terms of Green Economy indicators. Regarding the Carbon Emission status, the identified sector called agriculture and forestry is already low. After the green intervention, besides its complimentary support to other sector to be greener, managing the greenness of this sector is sufficient to lead the economy towards green on in the course of time.

To see whether Nepalese agriculture sector is resource efficient, we estimated Solow residual and calibrated the share of labor and capital in primary (agriculture), secondary and tertiary sectors. To assess the sources of growth and TFP, endogenous growth model has been estimated. The usual Cobb-Douglas constant returns to scale production function have been estimated by specifying the model in the following form: $Y_t = AK_t^\alpha L_t^\beta e^{\mu_t}$. Where, t is time subscript, Yt represents real output. A is total factor productivity parameter, Kt is real Capital stock, Lt is the Labor input, α and β are partial elasticity of output with respect to Capital and Labor respectively and μ_t is exponential of residual term. After estimating α and β , the output growth is attributed to total factor productivity growth through: $(\dot{T\hat{F}P}/T\hat{F}P) = (\dot{Y}/Y) - \hat{\alpha}(\dot{K}/K) - \hat{\beta}(\dot{L}/L)$. Variables having dot is the time differential as usual in common economics parlance. The OLS technique has been utilized for the estimation.

For sources of growth and factor returns including factor distribution to the capital and labor, some required variables were constructed based on available secondary data. In Nepal no readily capital stock variables are available. Such variables were computed following Khanal et. al. (2012). For the labor force and employment also, no time series data are readily available. Therefore, apart from census data, labor force surveys have used.

To check the gender inclusiveness in Agriculture sector, the NLSS-III data was used and usual tests were performed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The sources of growth in Nepal are estimated and the summary of findings is reported in table 4. It indicates that only the Labor remained the prime factor of Growth in Nepal during last 22 years. It has more than 91 % share in agriculture sector followed by 72.3 % in secondary and 96.6% in service sector. In totality, labor shares more than 88 % of growth in Nepal. It does not mean that capital did not play any role but, the per capita capital mixture needs some reshuffling. It can be assumed that the green economy intervention also seeks such reallocation of resources.

TABLE 4: Sources of Growth, Productivity and Distributional Gains

VARIABLES (In log level)	Primary GDP/ Capital	Secondary GDP/ Capital	Tertiary GDP/ Capital	Total GDP/ Capital
Share of Labor	0.915*** (0.0277)	0.723*** (0.165)	0.966*** (0.0442)	0.886*** (0.0247)
Constant	0.108* (0.0550)	1.342*** (0.459)	1.132*** (0.0737)	0.602*** (0.0360)
Observations	21	21	21	21
R-squared	0.993	0.541	0.992	0.995

To see the probable trade-offs of green intervention, a complete CGE modeling level of analysis is needed. Such type of analysis seeks huge resources and time. Still it can be signaled using the role of labor and capital in growth performance of the economy. Table 5 is the summary of the contributions from labor and capital. The coefficients in this table indicate that the TFP we can call it proxy to good governance here is negative in various years in Nepal. It is responsible for low growth. Still the labor is playing major role here. Now question arises, while shifting towards GE, we cannot compromise low growth. Therefore, blind initiation to GE may hamper the growth and productivity of the labor also.

Table 5: Contribution of Capital, Labor and Total Factor Productivity

Year	Growth Rate of GDP	Contribution from Capital	Contribution from Labor	TFP Growth Rate
>1980	2.34364	0.803693 (0.34%)	3.342472 (1.43%)	-1.80252 (-0.77%)
1985	4.896776	1.581534 (0.32%)	1.482112 (0.30%)	1.83313 (0.37%)
1990	5.14476	0.104522 (0.02%)	1.525946 (0.30%)	3.514292 (0.68%)
1995	5.080432	1.634865 (0.32%)	2.838011 (0.56%)	0.607556 (0.12%)

Year	Value	Percentage	Value	Percentage
2000	4.929969	0.285695	3.999415	0.644859
		(0.06%)	(0.81%)	(0.13%)
2005	2.462303	0.450371	2.861103	-0.84917
		(0.18%)	(1.16%)	(-0.34%)
2010 <	4.122913	0.702221	2.395372	1.02532
		(0.17%)	(0.58%)	(0.25%)

The contribution to growth from labor sector seems just right relative to other economies that fast growing economies like China and India also record the contribution of labor between 2 to 4 per cent alone from agriculture while growing by 8 to 10 per cent. And the capital also played big role in those economies. Therefore, while intervening in the spirit of GE framework, there might seem clear trade-off of growth and employment in Nepal. Another player in growth is TFP which contributed close to 7 per cent in China while growing by more than ten percent and it contributed more than 4 percent alone in India while she was growing by more than 8 per cent. In our case, the role of TFP is very peewee. Thus, while going to the GE, it must be kept in mind that whether TFP stimulates or not.

The GE framework assumes that Nepalese agriculture sector is inclusive. It remained the livelihood option for various marginalized and poor segment of the society. It is still to be tested. But, in terms of gender, the sector seemed very much biased, not inclusive. As agriculture related labor needed, we seek female labor significantly high scale. And, while paying in wage, we pay significantly low for the female. In terms of extra support to the labor like tiffin expenses and support in kind also female and biased treatment in Nepalese agriculture sector. If we convert all cash and kind wage in rupees term and test the average, it still reveals frustrating fact that female are significantly less paid.

Table 6: Gender wise average wage discrimination in Agriculture sector

Different Wages	Male	Female	N
Hires agriculture labor in wage*	8.8472 (6.88)	15.5930 (14.02)	3155
Daily Wage(NRS)*	123.39 (118.65)	85.23 (71.61)	3155
Extra daily wage in Kind(NRS)**	43.22 (71.70)	41.14 (55.45)	3155
Total wage(NRS)*	166.61 (150.69)	126.37 (98.92)	3155

Thus, while thinking of switching towards GE, this kind of green economy pillar should be kept in mind that green become really green.

CONCLUSION

Sufficient initiatives have been taken in Nepal regarding GE. Among them, it's good to know that the specific GE framework is under construction for periodic plan purpose. It is anticipated that the green growth intervention might breed high growth followed by more productive employment. Evidences show that, out of scanty growth performance in Nepal, the Labor played significantly pivotal role. The role of capital and good governance has yet to be improved. It is imperative to believe that the green economy

initiatives constrained by serious growth-employment trade-offs in Nepal. At the same time, the proposed green intervention on total factor productivity stipulation is unknown.

The proposed green growth framework assumes that Nepalese agriculture sector is inclusive. But the violation of one of the pillars of green economy, which is social pillar. Thus, while thinking of towards green economy, a serious country level study is must.

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